

VISCOSITY AND DENSITY OF CADMIUM CHLORIDE SOLUTIONS AT 35°.

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Viscosity and density of solutions of CdCl_2 both in water and hydrochloric acid (0.100 N) have been measured. Jones and Dole equation is applicable to both the solutions. The value of 'A' as found from aqueous solutions is 0.013 and 0.0079 for the hydrochloric acid solutions (for concentrations expressed in g. equivalents) as against 0.0099 calculated from Falkenhagen-Vernon equation for aqueous solutions. The values of 'B' are 0.131 for water and 0.117 for acid solutions. The applicability of Jones and Dole equation to hydrochloric acid solutions is surprising. It was expected that the electrical field in the solution due to the presence of other ions would make the equation inapplicable. The density of both the solutions increases linearly with concentration to an accuracy of 0.0001 for the dilute range.

The viscosity of aqueous solutions of cadmium chloride was studied, first to see whether it obeyed Jones and Dole equation (Jones and Dole, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 2950),

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$$

in the dilute range; and if it did, whether the value of 'A' was of the expected order (Falkenhagen and Vernon, *Phil. Mag.*, 1932, 14, 537). Some concentrated solutions too were examined. Some experiments were made with cadmium chloride dissolved in 0.100 N-hydrochloric acid as well.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental procedure followed as well as the dimensions of the pycnometer and viscometer were the same as described in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 301). As before, no kinetic and surface tension corrections were necessary. Five readings were taken for each solution. They seldom differed from one another by more than 0.2 second. Two readings for the pycnometer were taken and they always differed by less than 0.001 g. Double distilled water was used in making all the solutions.

The maximum possible error in the value of viscosity η/η_0 as found by assuming a maximum error of 0.2 second in time of transpiration and

0.001 g. in the weight of pycnometer comes out to be ± 0.0003 , but the actual error in most cases is expected to be much less.

In Table I concentration (c) of cadmium chloride in g. equivalents per litre, density (ρ) in g./c.c. and relative viscosity (η/η_0), hereafter called viscosity, are given.

TABLE I.

$c \times 10^4$.	ρ .	η/η_0 .		$c \times 10^4$.	ρ .	η/η_0 .	
		obs.	calc.			obs.	calc.
0	0.9941	1.0000	1.0000	456.0	0.9977	1.0087	1.0088
6.00	0.9941	1.0005	1.0004	570.0	0.9987	1.0109	1.0106
12.00	0.9941	1.0009	1.0006	684.0	0.9993	1.0117	1.0124
26.00	0.9943	1.0005	1.0010	798.0	1.0001	1.0143	1.0142
33.00	0.9943	1.0009	1.0011	864.0	1.0006	1.0150	1.0151
43.00	0.9944	1.0013	1.0015	972.0	1.0014	1.0172	1.0168
51.00	0.9945	1.0016	1.0016	1080	1.0024	1.0086	1.0185
60.00	0.9947	1.0019	1.0018	1140	1.0105	1.0331	1.0345
68.00	0.9948	1.0022	1.0020	1210	1.0184	1.0483	1.0494
77.00	0.9948	1.0025	1.0021	1280	1.0271	1.0637	1.0644
85.00	0.9950	1.0025	1.0023	1350	1.0347	1.0776	...
99.00	0.9948	1.0028	1.0026	1420	1.0428	1.0925	...
110.0	0.9949	1.0032	1.0028	1390	1.0516	1.1080	...
114.0	0.9950	1.0031	1.0029	1440	1.0587	1.1226	...
228.0	0.9959	1.0047	1.0050	1950	1.0675	1.1398	...
342.0	0.9968	1.0072	1.0069	10700	1.0747	1.1532	...

In Table II, the concentration (c) of cadmium chloride in 0.100N-hydrochloric acid, density and viscosity are given.

TABLE II.

$c \times 10^4$.	ρ .	η/η_0 .		$c \times 10^4$.	ρ .	η/η_0 .	
		obs.	calc.			obs.	calc.
0	0.9958	1.0081	1.0081	90.00	0.9965	1.0094	1.0100
10.00	0.9963	1.0086	1.0085	100.0	0.9966	1.0096	1.0101
20.00	0.9961	1.0089	1.0087	200.0	0.9975	1.0114	1.0115
34.00	0.9961	1.0089	1.0090	300.0	0.9983	1.0135	1.0130
40.00	0.9963	1.0088	1.0091	400.0	0.9990	1.0150	1.0144
50.00	0.9963	1.0089	1.0093	500.0	0.9998	1.0159	1.0158
60.00	0.9963	1.0090	1.0094	600.0	1.0007	1.0167	1.0171
70.00	0.9964	1.0093	1.0096	700.0	1.0014	1.0184	1.0184
80.00	0.9965	1.0097	1.0097	800.0	1.0022	1.0196	1.0198

In the figure $(\eta/\eta_0 - 1/\sqrt{c})$ for aqueous solutions is plotted against $\sqrt{c}$, i.e., against square root of equivalent concentration. A similar figure is obtained in the case of hydrochloric acid solutions also.

DISCUSSION.

Viscosity of Aqueous Solutions.—In the figure a straight line ($A = 0.013$ and $B = 0.131$) is obtained. The value of 'A' as calculated from Falkenhagen-Vernon equation (*loc. cit.*) by taking the dielectric constant of water to be 74 at 35°, and by using extrapolated values of the ionic conductivities of Cd^{++} and Cl^- given in Landolt-Börnstein tables, is 0.014 when c is expressed in g. mols. and so 0.0099 when c is in g. equivalents, as against 0.013 found by actual experiment. The two values are of the same order. The calculated values of viscosity are given in Table I. The calculated viscosities

for seventeen out of twenty-two solutions (range tenth normal) agree with the observed values within experimental error (± 0.0003). In three, the difference rises upto 0.0004, in one upto 0.0005 and in one upto 0.0007.

Density of Aqueous Solutions.—Density of aqueous solutions increases almost linearly with concentration and can be represented almost within experimental error (± 0.0001) upto a concentration of 0.2140 by the equation: $\rho = 0.9941 + 0.0773c$. Beyond this concentration, the variations become wider and are not within the limits of experimental error.

Viscosity of HCl-CdCl₂ Solutions.—All the solutions were made in 0.100-N-hydrochloric acid solution ($\rho = 0.9958$, $\eta/\eta_0 = 1.0081$). These experiments were performed to see whether hydrochloric acid in the solutions behaved as a mere solvent or exerted such electrical forces on the ions of CdCl₂ as to render Jones and Dole equation inapplicable. In this case, $\eta/\eta_0 - 1.0081/\sqrt{c}$ was plotted against $\sqrt{c}$. A straight line ($\eta/\eta_0 = 1.0081 + 0.0080\sqrt{c} + 0.117c$ or $\eta/\eta_{\text{HCl}} = 1 + 0.0079\sqrt{c} + 0.116c$) was obtained

which represents the viscosity of all the solutions quite well, though the difference between the observed and the calculated values in many cases (*vide* Table II) exceeds the possible experimental error (± 0.0003). The only perceptible effect of the hydrochloric acid solution is the lowering of the value of *A* from 0.013 to 0.0079 and of *B* from 0.131 to 0.116. Otherwise, hydrochloric acid behaves as a mere solvent.

Density of HCl-CdCl₂ Solutions.—Density of the solutions increases linearly throughout and can be represented by the equation, $\rho = 0.9958 + 0.0807c$ to an accuracy of $\pm 0.0001g$.

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